

CHARACTERIZATION OF MODE II INTERLAMINAR CRACK GROWTH BASED ON ANALYTICAL COMPLIANCE METHOD

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ABSTRACT

A new method of end notched flexure test has been proposed for characterization of the mode II interlaminar crack growth. A special COD gauge has been developed for the measurement of crack opening displacement (COD) of ENF specimen. Crack initiation can be detected with very high accuracy from the load-COD diagram. Moreover, crack propagation is stable under the constant COD condition. An analytical compliance method has successfully applied to the ENF test, and the change of G_{IIC} from initiation to stable propagation can be obtained automatically by using a computer aided testing system.

INTRODUCTION

End Notched Flexure (ENF) test¹ is widely accepted to determine the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates. In the case of conventional ENF test, the crack growth is unstable², and the fracture toughness, G_{IIC} , is determined at the onset of crack initiation. The crack growth behavior can not be characterized.

A stabilized ENF test is proposed in the present method for characterization of mode II interlaminar crack growth. Crack opening displacement (COD) of the ENF specimen is measured by a COD gauge, and the test is carried out under constant COD speed because the crack growth becomes stable. An analytical compliance method³, which has been proposed by one of authors, is applied to the ENF test in order to estimate G_{IIC} and crack length during the crack propagation.

ANALYTICAL COMPLIANCE METHOD

1. Finite Element Analysis of ENF Specimen

ENF specimen as shown in Fig. 1 is analyzed numerically by using a finite element method. $2L$ is span length, a is crack length, $2H$ is thickness, B is width and E_L is longitudinal modulus for bending. COD and δ are crack opening displacement and load-point displacement, respectively, at the applied load, P . The distribution of the contact stress due

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Fig. 1 ENF Specimen

Fig. 2 Distribution of Contact Stress

Fig. 3 Mesh Pattern for Finite Element Analysis

to crack closure is assumed to be sinusoidal as shown in Fig. 2. The total contact force is equal to $P/4$. Changing the size of contact area to satisfy the boundary condition on crack surfaces, we have found the optimum size is $3H$. Breakdown of the finite element model is shown in Fig. 3. COD and δ are calculated as the functions of crack length. The COD compliance, λ , and the load-point compliance, C , are obtained as the ratios of COD/P and δ/P , respectively.

The relation between the normalized crack length, a/H , and the square root of normalized COD compliance, γ_{COD} , is obtained as a simple linear equation from the numerical analysis. The coefficients are obtained by the least squares method.

$$\frac{a}{H} = A_0 + A_1 \gamma_{COD} \quad , \quad \gamma_{COD} = \sqrt{BE_L \lambda} \quad (1)$$

The relation between COD compliance and load-point compliance is obtained in much the same way. The coefficients, A_i and B_i , are given in Table 1.

$$\gamma_{\delta} = B_0 + B_1 \gamma_{COD} \quad , \quad \gamma_{\delta} = \left[BE_L C - \frac{1}{4} \cdot \left(\frac{L}{H} \right)^3 \right]^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

The energy release rate, G_{II} , is obtained from Eqs. (1) and (2).

$$G_{II} = \frac{3}{2E_L H} \left(\frac{P}{B} \right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{B_1}{A_1} \right) \cdot (B_0 + B_1 \gamma_{COD})^2 \quad (3)$$

Table 1 Coefficients A_i and B_i in Eqs. (1) and (2)

A_0	A_1	B_0	B_1
-0.667	0.821	0.896	0.568

The crack length and energy release rate can be obtained analytically from the COD compliance without direct measurement of crack length.

2. Stability of Crack Growth

Stability of crack propagation is discussed based on the elementary beam theory. For ENF specimen under constant load-point displacement (fixed grip) condition, dG_{II}/da is obtained as²

$$\frac{dG_{II}}{da} = \frac{9\delta^2 a}{8E_L B^2 H^3 C^2} \left[1 - \frac{9a^2}{2L^3 + 3a^3} \right] \quad (4)$$

Stable crack growth requires dG_{II}/da to be less than or equal to zero. This gives

$$a \geq L / \sqrt[3]{3} \approx 0.7L$$

Consequently, for the commonly used $a \approx L/2$, the crack growth is unstable.

Under constant COD condition, on the other hand, dG_{II}/da is obtained as

$$\frac{dG_{II}}{da} = - \frac{9COD^2 a}{8E_L B^2 H^3 \lambda^2} \quad (5)$$

This quantity is always negative, and thus the crack growth is stable in the case of the COD-control ENF test.

Fig. 4 COD Gauge for ENF Specimen

TEST METHOD

1. Material and Specimen

Material tested is unidirectionally reinforced carbon/epoxy laminate which is made from Toray P305 prepregs (T300/#2500). The nominal thickness of the lamina and laminate are 0.25 mm and 3.0 mm, respectively. The nominal fiber volume fraction is 60 %. The elastic moduli measured by four-point bend test are as follows;

$$E_L = 113 \text{ GPa}, E_T = 7.8 \text{ GPa}, G_{LT} = 4.1 \text{ GPa} \text{ and } \nu_{LT} = 0.34$$

The ENF specimens are machined and finished with dimensions of

$$2L = 100 \text{ mm}, B = 25 \text{ mm}, 2H = 3 \text{ mm}, a_0 \approx 25 \text{ mm}$$

PTFE film with length of 20 mm is inserted as a starter crack. The crack is carefully wedged open and extended about 5 mm beyond the insert in order to introduce a natural starter crack.

2. COD Gauge

A special COD gauge as shown in Fig. 4 has been developed in order to measure the COD of ENF specimen. The relative deformation of the upper and lower crack surfaces is detected by a cantilever of the COD gauge and converted into voltage by using strain gauges. Working distance of the COD gauge is 1 mm. The COD gauge is calibrated with a micrometer.

3. Test Procedure

An MTS electrohydraulic testing machine is used for the COD-controlled ENF test. The output signal of COD gauge is selected to be the control variable, and the closed-loop control makes COD speed constant with crack propagation. The COD speed was chosen to be 0.03 mm/min in the present paper. Unloading and re-loading took place several times during the test to obtain the compliance data as shown in Fig. 5. The procedure is performed in much the same way as DCB test, but it is impossible to measure crack length by using traveling microscope because the crack propagates in the pure mode II. Analytical compliance method based on Eqs. (1) and (3) is applied to determine the crack length. In order to examine validity the method, crack length is measured by opening the specimen into two parts after completion of the test.

5% less secant line is used in order to determine the fracture toughness at crack initiation. The method is in much the same way as ASTM E399 standard.

Fig. 5 An Example of Load versus COD Diagram

4. Computer Aided Testing System

Control of testing machine, data acquisition and analysis of experimental data have been carried out automatically by a computer. Analog signals from the load cell and COD gauge are converted into digital signals and stored in the memory of CPU and hard disks. From the digital data of load vs COD diagram during the unloading and re-loading processes, the COD compliance is determined by using the least squares method. Crack length and fracture toughness are calculated from the compliance by using the analytical compliance method.

Fig. 6 An Example of G_{IIC} versus Crack Length Curve

Fig. 7 Relation between Square Root of Normalized COD Compliance and Normalized Crack Length

Fig. 8 Relation between Normalized COD Compliance and Normalized Load-Point Compliance

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

An example of interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IIC} , vs crack length diagram is shown in Fig. 6. Points marked by \bullet and \circ represent the results from the COD compliance during unloading and reloading, respectively. The interpolating curve is the result during the crack propagation obtained by calibrating the effect of permanent deflection. Fig. 7 represents an experimental relation between the crack length and the COD compliance with the numerical result of Eq. (1). Experimental and numerical relations between the COD compliance and the load-point compliance are shown in Fig. 8. Agreement between the experimental and numerical results are excellent. Validity of the analytical compliance method is confirmed.

Interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IICi} , at crack initiation is listed in Table 2. The critical load is determined by the ASTM E399 method and the maximum load. G_{IICi} values are calculated by the present analysis and the elementary beam theory¹.

Fig. 9 depicts the change of G_{IIC} with crack propagation. G_{IIC} is nearly constant during the stable crack growth and the average value of the five specimens is 0.643 kJ/m^2 . the scatter of experimental data is small.

Fig. 9 Fracture Toughness during Stable Crack Growth

Table 2 Interlaminar Fracture Toughness, G_{IIc_i} , at Crack Initiation

Equations of G_{II}	Present Analysis	Elementary Beam Theory (Ref.1)	
Estimation of Critical Load	5% less secant line	(ASTM E399)	Maximum Load
Average of G_{IIc_i} (kJ/m ²) (n=5)	0.568	0.554	0.585

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The crack growth of ENF specimen is stable under COD-control and the analytical compliance method is successfully applied to determine G_{IIc} and the crack length. The crack initiation is detected from the load vs COD diagram with high accuracy by using 5% less secant line proposed in ASTM E399 standard.

G_{IIc_i} obtained by the E399 method is about 5% smaller than at the maximum load. The result indicates that subcritical crack growth exists even in the brittle composites such as carbon/epoxy system. Difference between Eq. (3) and beam theory is negligible. G_{IIc} is nearly constant during the stable crack growth. The value is 15-20 % higher than G_{IIc_i} .

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is a part of MITI program of Basic Technology for Future Industry and financially supported by the Agency of Industrial Science and Technology, Ministry of International Trade and Industry, Japan.

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